

Machine Learning Based on Neural Network Model for User Behavior Prediction in Online Advertising

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Abstract: This paper compares and analyzes the DA-FM and Fi-HGNN models using the publicly available datasets Criteo and Avazu. The experimental results demonstrate that the DA-FM model and Fi-HGNN model suggested in this thesis outperform similar models in the datasets, as evidenced by better AUC values. Consequently, the CTR prediction results are more precise. Simultaneously, the impact of each module is validated by ablation experiments, demonstrating that the significance of directing attention towards characteristics in two distinct manners is advantageous for enhancing the predictive capability of the model. Furthermore, empirical studies have demonstrated that employing heterogeneous graph neural networks enhances the model's capacity to represent and interact with features, thereby leading to improved prediction accuracy.

Keywords: Comparison; UBP; Advertising

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1. Design Background and Improvement Ideas

In advertising click scenes, there are many category and numerical features, such as personal attribute characteristics such as age, gender, occupation, income, hobbies, as well as contextual features such as advertising type, form, and location. And each field has multiple attribute values, such as {hobby: basketball; Football; Billiards, profession: teacher; Programmers; Civil servants, etc. Therefore, as shown in Figure1, there are semantic differences between different field domains, and there is a certain correlation between feature attributes in the same field domain. The relationship between feature fields and feature attributes is an interlayer relationship.

Figure 1 Relationship between feature fields and attributes

Currently, most click through rate models first map features to the same embedding space for representation and use structures such as factor decomposition machines or deep neural networks to combine low order and high-order features. However, embedding features into the same space cannot model the semantic differences of features and cannot reflect the hierarchical relationship between fields and attributes.

Therefore, this article adopts heterogeneous graph embedding technology to model the semantics of features, and then uses hierarchical attention structure to model feature attributes and field relationships, proposing a Feature Interaction via Heterogeneous Graph Neural Networks (Fi-HGNN) based model.

2 Fi-HGNN Network Architecture Design

The structure of Fi-HGNN is shown in Figure 2. The model consists of five parts: input layer, weighted embedding layer, composition layer, feature interaction layer, and output layer. In Chapter 4, this paper verifies the feasibility and effectiveness of ECA-NET in calculating input feature weights through experiments. Therefore, in the weighted embedding layer, we use ECA NET to represent the embedding vector with weight. Construct a feature heterogeneity graph representation in the composition layer, interact with the node attributes and semantic attributes of the features in the feature interaction layer, obtain high-order composite features by iterating multiple interaction layers, and finally input the high-order features into the fully connected network to obtain prediction results.

Figure2 Fi-HGNN network structure diagram

2.1 Input Layer

Firstly, the category features are one hot encoded, and then concatenated with numerical features as input to the model. In the weighted embedding layer, the high-dimensional sparse vector is first multiplied by the Emedding matrix to obtain a low dimensional dense vector, where the embedding layer principle is described. Then, the low dimensional dense vector is calculated using ECANET to calculate the corresponding weights of the vector. Finally, the weighted embedding vector ECA-LIKE Embedding is obtained by multiplying the embedding vector with the weight vector. The principle of ECA-NET is described. The mathematical representation of the weighted embedding vector is shown in formula (1)

$$e'_i = f_{ECANET}(e_i) \tag{1}$$

2.2 Feature Interaction Layer

To capture the differences between different fields, nodes should be embedded in different distributed mapping spaces. The model maps different feature fields into heterogeneous graph nodes of different colors in the composition module. In order to model the heterogeneity of nodes, formula (2) needs to be used for different types of input nodes before feature interaction.

After calculating the similarity, the weights are weighted and summed with the original feature attributes to obtain the representation of the domain feature state vector, as shown in formula (5.2), where σ represents the activation function sigmoid.

$$\tilde{h}_{F_i}^{\varphi(i)} = \sigma \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \beta_{ik}^{\varphi(i)} \cdot \tilde{h}_{f_i}^{\varphi(i)} \right) \tag{2}$$

Due to the scale-free nature of heterogeneous graphs, the variance of graph data is quite high. To address this issue, Fi-HGNN extends attribute level attention to multi head attention, making the training process more stable. The calculation method is shown in formula (5.3). Among them, Δ represents concatenation operation, which involves concatenating N repeatedly learned domain states to obtain the i-th domain feature vector state representation.

$$\tilde{h}_{F_i}^\varphi = \prod_{n=1, \dots, N} \sigma \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \beta_{ik}^{\varphi(i)} \cdot \tilde{h}_{F_i}^{\varphi(i)} \right) \quad (3)$$

The aggregation of node neighbor information is shown in Figures 5-5.

Due to the strength of different domain features when combined, in order to characterize the interaction strength between different nodes, Fi-HGNN uses an attention mechanism to calculate edge weights, as shown in formula (5.4). Where σ represents the activation function LeakyRelu, and W_w is the weight matrix.

$$\gamma_{ij} = \frac{\exp \left(\sigma \left(W_w^K \left[\tilde{h}_{F_i}^\varphi, \tilde{h}_{F_j}^\varphi \right] \right) \right)}{\sum_{k=1}^m \exp \left(\sigma \left(W_w^K \left[\tilde{h}_{F_i}^\varphi, \tilde{h}_{F_j}^\varphi \right] \right) \right)} \quad (4)$$

3 Results and Analysis

The experimental results of different models in two datasets, where Fi HGNN+ represents the combination of DA-FM and Fi HGNN in a parallel structure, with shallow model DA-FM used on the wide side and deep model Fi HGNN used on the deep side. The Fi HGNN++ model combines Fi HGNN and DNN in a parallel structure, with the wide side using the Fi HGNN model and the deep side using DNN. Bold the optimal results for different types of models.

Logistic regression models are lower than other models that introduce combined features, and high-order models generally perform better than low-order models, proving that it is feasible to improve model prediction accuracy by constructing combined features in click through rate prediction tasks. The performance of DeepCrossing models is far inferior to AutoInt and Fi GNN models, possibly due to the implicit construction of high-order features using DNN, which cannot model complex feature relationships in a flexible manner. AutoInt explicitly models feature interactions through a multi head self attention network, while Fi-GNN transforms traditional feature interaction methods into aggregation and updating of graph node information by constructing heterogeneous feature maps. Therefore, compared to implicitly constructing high-order features, the explicit modeling method using attention mechanism and graph neural network performs better and can dynamically characterize feature interaction relationships.

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By comparing the Fi-HGNN, Fi-HGNN+, and Fi-HGNN++ models, it can be found that capturing both low order and high-order explicit features in a parallel structure, as well as introducing high-order implicit features, can both improve the predictive performance of the model. It can be seen that the improvement of the Fi HGNN+ and Fi HGNN++ models is relatively small, indicating that the Fi HGNN model itself has very good predictive ability.

By analyzing Table, it can be concluded that removing any module will result in a decrease in model performance. The performance of the Fi-HGNN (- T) model shows the most significant decline, with a larger decrease than the Fi-HGNN (- A) model. It is important to focus on the semantic differences of different field features and construct accurate feature vector space representations, rather than focusing on the strength of feature combinations. The Fi-HGNN (- A) model with the attention edge weight module removed has a smaller performance improvement than the Fi-HGNN model, indicating that using heterogeneous graphs instead of homogeneous graphs for feature information modeling is effective.

The number of heterogeneous layers T is an important hyperparameter that affects the performance of the Fi-HGNN model. When there is only one layer of heterogeneous graph, the model performs the worst because the graph nodes only obtain the current input feature information; After 3 layers of heterogeneous graph iteration, the model achieved

the best performance, and the graph nodes were able to fully aggregate neighboring node information and update their own node states; When the number of iterations reaches 4, due to the redundancy of information aggregated by graph nodes, the model exhibits overfitting and performance tends to decline. Therefore, the Fi-HGNN model uses a three-layer heterogeneity map for high-order feature combination on both datasets.

Table 5-1 Comparison prediction results

Model	Criteo		Avazu	
	Auc	Logloss	Auc	Logloss
LR	0.762	0.466	0.736	0.392
FM	0.772	0.478	0.746	0.416
AFM	0.794	0.458	0.772	0.385
SE-FM	0.795	0.453	0.773	0.385
DA-FM(ours)	0.796	0.452	0.775	0.383
DeepCrossing	0.801	0.451	0.764	0.389
AutoInt	0.806	0.446	0.775	0.382
Fi-GNN	0.806	0.445	0.776	0.383
Fi-HGNN(ours)	0.809	0.444	0.777	0.382
Wide&Deep	0.803	0.449	0.775	0.382
DeepFM	0.807	0.445	0.775	0.383
DCN	0.807	0.445	0.773	0.384
Fi-HGNN+(ours)	0.809	0.443	0.778	0.381
Fi-HGNN++(ours)	0.810	0.443	0.778	0.381

4 Summary

The existing click through rate prediction models embed feature vectors into the same space, which makes it difficult to reflect the semantic differences of multi domain classification field features. The use of DNN structures to implicitly extract higher-order features limits the model's ability to model complex interactions between different features in a flexible and explicit manner. This chapter proposes a feature crossover model based on heterogeneous graph neural network, Fi-HGNN, to address the issues of semantic differences and explicit feature interaction in feature fields. In terms of input feature representation, the Fi-HGNN model first uses ECA NET to weight and re represent the embedding vectors, and then models the semantic properties of the classification field features using heterogeneous graphs. In terms of feature interaction, Fi-HGNN uses type conversion, hierarchical attention to aggregate node interaction information with neighboring node information, GRU structure for node state updates, and iterative multiple graph neural layers to achieve explicit high-order feature interaction. The Fi-HGNN model, which constructs heterogeneous graph neural networks for feature representation and interaction, performs better than lower order models, higher-order neural network models, attention network models, and homogeneous graph neural network models. It can be seen that using heterogeneous graphs to obtain refined field feature vector representations and updating the sequence states of graph nodes can improve the predictive ability of the model. In the ablation experiment, removing the type conversion module or attention edge weight module resulted in a decrease in model performance. Removing the type conversion module related to heterogeneous graphs will result in a significant decrease in the performance of Fi-HGNN, indicating that it is more important to focus on the input representation of multi domain classification fields.

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